

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Shoira Eshboyeva

“DEVONI LUG‘OTIT TURK” ASARIDAGI IJRO HOLATI FE‘LLARI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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